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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of Polyherbal Toothpaste

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ABSTRACT

Toothpaste is a gel or paste formulation product and is used to clean and maintain oral hygiene with the aid of toothbrush. The majority of the cleaning is performed by the mechanical utilisation of the toothbrush with the help of excipients used in toothpaste. The aim of this investigation is to evaluate herbal toothpaste formulation. Herbal toothpaste with natural ingredients is more acceptable in public opinion than chemical-based formulation due to their safety and efficacy in reducing dental caries and preventing other dental disorders. The objective of the present research work is to formulate herbal toothpaste containing natural ingredients like Neem, Clove, Black-seed oil and walnut. These extracts have anti-bacterial, anti-caries, anti-ulcer, anti-oxidant and anti-fungal activities. The physicochemical evaluation of selected plants were within the pharmacopoeial limit and phytochemical screening in ethanol and water extracts showed the intensive presence of constituents like Alkaloid, Flavonoids, Glycosides, Phenols and tannins. The formulated herbal toothpaste were evaluated to determine important physical characteristics such as pH, Foamability, Spreadability, Abrasiveness, Extrudability and Shape retention in order to develop a more effective and stable product. All in-vitro evaluations of prepared herbal toothpaste showed better result. The developed formulation showed anti-bacterial activity against bacterial culture and produced a better zone of inhibition. The purpose of this project is to make and test the prepared herbal toothpaste. This research proves that our herbal based toothpaste formulation with natural ingredients is excellent as it gets in terms of performance.

INTRODUCTION

COSMETICS

As per drug and cosmetics Act 1940 and Rules 1945 “Cosmetics is defined as any article intended

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to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled or sprayed on or introduced into, or otherwise applied to the human body or any part therefore cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance.

HERBAL COSMETICS

Herbal cosmetics are formulated using different cosmetic ingredients to form the base in which one or more herbal ingredients are used to cure various skin ailments. Plants are highly used for the development of new drug products for cosmeceuticals and pharmaceutical applications.

HERBAL TOOTHPASTE

Toothpaste is a paste or gel dentifrice used with a toothbrush as an accessory to clean and maintain the aesthetics and health of our teeth promoting oral hygiene. Nowadays most of the toothpaste contains chemicals that produce harmful effect to the teeth and gums hence herbal toothpaste is a wise and healthier choice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of plant material

The fresh plant parts of *Azadirachta indica*, *syzygium aromaticum*, and *Juglans regia* were collected from Kasaragod and Kannur districts, Kerala (India) in the month of March 2024.

Authentication of plant material

The plant material was identified and authenticated by Smitha K.O, Assistant professor

(Department of Horticulture), College of Agriculture, Padannakad, Kasaragod, Kerala. *Azadirachta indica*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, and *Juglans regia* were dried under shade.

Preparation of plant extracts

The collected plant materials are carefully washed under water and was dried at shade for 10-15 days. These shade dried plant material were homogenized to a coarse powder using an electronic blender and then stored at air tight container until further use .The organic solvents such as ethanol and water was used for extraction .10 gm of homogenized coarse leaf powder of *Azadirachta indica*, *Syzygium aromaticum*, and *Juglans regia* was soaked in different conical flasks containing 100 ml of ethanol and water .Then it is allowed to stand 30 minutes with occasional shaking, finally each sample extract was filtered through whatmanNO:1 filter paper .This filtrate used to detect various biologically active constituents present in various solvent extract.

Preliminary phytochemical screening

The extracts were subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening to detect the various phytoconstituents such as alkaloids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, tannins and phenols.

Formulation of polyherbal toothpaste

Sr. No.	Ingredients(gm)	Quantity(w/w) %			Functions
		F1	F2	F3	
1.	Neem	1.5gm	1.5gm	1gm	Prevent dental plaque
2	Clove	0.5gm	1gm	1gm	Analgesic
3	Walnut	1.5gm	1gm	1gm	Teeth whitening
4	Blackseed oil	2ml	1ml	1ml	Anti-dental caries
5	Calcium carbonate	12.5gm	12.5gm	12.5gm	Abrasive
6	Glycerin	2.5ml	2.5ml	2.5ml	Humectant
7	Sodium lauryl sulphate	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	Detergent
8	Tragacanth gum	0.25gm	0.25gm	0.25gm	Suspending agent
9	Sodium chloride	0.25gm	0.25gm	0.25gm	Anti-cavities
10	Sodium saccharine	0.25gm	0.25gm	0.25gm	Sweetener
11	Propyl paraben	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	Preservatives

12	Carboxy methyl cellulose	0.25gm	0.25gm	0.25gm	Binding agent
13	Distilled water	10ml	10ml	10ml	Vehicle

Procedure

1. Neem, Clove, Walnut were added to mortar and triturated with the help of pestle.
2. Then sodium lauryl sulphate, calcium carbonate and sodium saccharin are added.
3. Further glycerin, tragacanth, carboxy methyl cellulose are added and mixed well.
4. Finally sodium chloride and propyl paraben were added to the above mixture. Then the powder mixture is converted to paste by adding distilled water and triturates until a thick paste is obtained. Finally black seed oil was added to above.

Methods of evaluation

A. Physical Evaluation

Physical parameters such as color and appearance were evaluated.

B.Determination of pH

Take one gram of the toothpaste in a 150ml beaker and add 10ml of freshly boiled and cooled water. Stir well to make a thorough suspension and determine the pH of the suspension using pH meter.

C.Foamability

2g of toothpaste was measured and mixed with 5ml of water in a measuring cylinder. Shake it for 10minutes and final volume was taken.

Foamability =Final Volume-Initial volume

D. Determination of spreadability

Slip and drag characteristics of paste are used to determine the spreadability technique. About 1-2g of herbal toothpaste was weighed and placed between two glass slides (10×10) that were stacked one on top of the other, and then slides were moved in opposite directions. After 3 minutes measure the amount of toothpaste that has spread. Repeat three times.

$$S=M \times L/T$$

M- Weight placed

L-Length moved by glass slide

T-Time taken to separate upper slide from lower

E.Extrudability

In this method, the formulated paste was filled in standard capped collapsible aluminum tube and sealed by crimping to the end. The weights of tubes were recorded. The tubes were placed between two glass slides and were clamped.500g was placed over the slides and then cap was removed. The amount of the extruded paste was collected and weighed. The percent of the extruded paste was calculated.

F.Abrasiveness

Extrude the content 15-20cm long on through the butter paper. Repeat the same process for at least ten collapsible tubes. Press the contents of the entire length with fingertip for the presence of sharp- and hard- edged abrasive particles.

G.Fragrance test

It was based on individual observation for its acceptability. Five people were asked for acceptability of fragrance and their opinion was taken and fragrance was evaluated based on the below described criteria.

- A. The fragrance was good, as good as the fragrance of reference toothpaste.
- B. The fragrance of the toothpaste was not good but comparable to the reference toothpaste.
- C. C)The fragrance of the toothpaste was poor than reference toothpaste.

H. Shape retention

Toothpaste was squeezed out from the tube and put under the toothbrush and the state of the toothpaste after it was allowed to stand for 10seconds was evaluated based on the,

- A. Shape just after the toothpaste is squeezed out on the toothbrush is maintained.

B. Shape just after the toothpaste is squeezed at on the toothbrush is almost maintained.

C. C)The toothpaste squeezed from the toothbrush and cannot maintain its shape.

Screening for antimicrobial activity

Antimicrobial activity was determined by agar well diffusion method using ampicillin as standard. Activity of herbal toothpaste was tested against E. coli and lactobacillus. The required amount of agar was prepared and inoculated into it by microorganisms. Then agar solution was poured into the petri plates and allowed to stand to solidify for a few minutes. After, solidification a sterilized

well digger was used to generate the appropriate size of wells. The toothpaste are then filled in. The plates were incubated in inverted condition at 37°C for 48 hours. After 48 hours, the plates were observed for the presence of inhibition of bacterial growth, and it was indicated in the form of a clear zone of inhibition. The zone of inhibition obtained for the developed herbal toothpaste was compared with the standard Ampicillin.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Phytochemicals present in ethanol and aqueous extracts of Azadirachta indica, Syzygium aromaticum and Juglans regia.

SL NO.	Chemical constituents	Azadirachta indica		Syzygium aromaticum		Juglans regia	
		Water extract	Ethanol extract	Water extract	Ethanol extract	Water extract	Ethanol extract
1	Alkaloids	+	+	-	+	+	+
2	Carbohydrate	-	-	-	+	+	-
3	Flavonoids	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	Saponins	+	-	-	-	+	+
5	Glycosides	-	+	-	-	-	+
6	Tannins	+	+	+	+	+	+
7	Phenols	+	+	-	-	+	+

Evaluation of polyherbal toothpaste

A. Physical evaluation

Physical parameters such as color and appearance were evaluated.

Sr No.	Parameters	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3
1.	Colour	Ash	Ash	Ash
2.	Oduor	Pleasant	Pleasant	Pleasant
3.	Taste	Sweet	Sweet	Sweet
4.	Smoothness	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

B. Determination of Ph

	F1	F2	F3
pH	7.11	7.23	7.46

C. Foamability

	F1	F2	F3
Foamability	6ml	8ml	9ml

D. Determination of Spreadability

	F1	F2	F3
Spreadability	2.4cm/sec	2.6cm/sec	2.9cm/sec

E. Extrudability

SL	Extrudability	Observation		
		F1	F2	F3

NO				
1	Net wt. of formulation in tube (gm)	15.00gm	15.02gm	15.01gm
2	Wt. of toothpaste extruded(gm)	12.12gm	12.3gm	12.4gm
3	Extrudability amount percentage	80.8%	81.89%	82.61%

F. Abrasiveness

The abrasiveness of herbal toothpaste F3 was found to be good.

G. Fragrance test

SL NO	Observer	Opinion		
		F1	F2	F3
1	Tester 1	B	A	A
2	Tester 2	A	C	B
3	Tester 3	C	B	A
4	Tester 4	A	C	B
5	Tester 5	B	B	A

H. Shape retention

Toothpaste was squeezed out from the tube and put entirely on a toothbrush and the state of the toothpaste after it was allowed to stand for 10 seconds was evaluated in F3 formulation as, Shape just after the toothpaste is squeezed out on the toothbrush is maintained.

Screening for antimicrobial activity

The developed formulations showed anti-bacterial activity against Lactobacillus and E. coli produced a better zone of inhibition of about 5mm,6mm respectively which was near to the zone of inhibition produced by standard Ampicillin (10mm,8mm).

Diameter of the zone of inhibition(mm)			
Sr. No.	Bacteria	Ampicillin	Herbal Toothpaste (F3)
1.	Lactobacillus	10	5
2.	E. coli	8	6

DISCUSSION

The present work is to develop toothpaste containing herbal ingredients to be applied in the treatment of tooth decay and prevent dental plaque and whitens teeth. Continuous usage of synthetic agent containing toothpaste causes various side effects such as altered taste, discoloured teeth etc. in order to overcome these problems associated with synthetic agent's herbal toothpaste were considered as the better choice. There is a greater possibility in the development of herbal formulation as it is safe, effective, convenient and economic. The main aim of the study is to make herbal toothpaste using herbal plants such as Azadirachta indica, Syzygium aromaticum,

Nigella sativa and Juglans regia. The plants were selected on the basis of their therapeutic potential, antibacterial activity, and selective therapeutic action on oral cavity. The pH of the herbal toothpaste was found to be 7.46 which lies in alkaline prance do not produce any irritation upon buccal cavity, and it complied with BIS limit. The spreadability of herbal toothpaste was good. The internal part of all collapsible tubes has no signs of corrosion or damage during the normal storage conditions at a temperature of 45 degree Celsius for 10 days. The foamability of herbal toothpaste was good (9ml). The herbal toothpaste shows good abrasiveness and 82.61% of extrudability. The antibacterial activity of the developed herbal

toothpaste was done by agar well diffusion method using Ampicillin as the standard drug. The developed formulations showed anti-bacterial activity against *Lactobacillus* and *E.coli* produced a better zone of inhibition of about 5mm,6mm respectively which was near to the zone of inhibition produced by standard Ampicillin (10mm,8mm).It was concluded that the developed herbal toothpaste posses all desirable properties of an ideal herbal toothpaste.

CONCLUSION:

The aim of study is to formulate herbal toothpaste using *Azadirachta indica*, *syzygium aromaticum*, *Juglans regia* and *Nigella sativa* oil. Physicochemical and phytochemical properties of these plant parts have been reported in this thesis work.The preliminary phytochemical screening of these plant shows the presence of major constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, glycosides, tannins and phenols have been known to be biologically active and thus partially responsible for the antimicrobial activity. The herbal toothpaste formulated by using extracts of *Azadirachta indica* and *Syzygium aromaticum* and *juglans regia*. The table 3 (F3) presented the outcome. From the result revealed that the prepared herbal toothpaste was good in appearance, easily spreadable, good abrasiveness, extrudability, foamability.The in-vitro antibacterial evaluation was done by using agar well diffusion method and antibacterial activity was measured in terms of zone of inhibition. The formulation shows a better zone of inhibition against *Lactobacillus* and *E. coli* bacteria which was near to the zone of inhibition produced by standard ampicillinFollowing conclusion can be drawn from the results obtained in the present work of investigation. This herbal toothpaste is having prominent function in the maintaining of the oral hygiene and preventing dental caries and are safer with minimum side effect than chemical based synthetic toothpaste. The formulated herbal

toothpaste has good scope in future in nature remedies research, reduced cost and improve dental health of public.

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